

A Modified SVD Based Face Recognition using Hidden Markov Models

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Abstract—In this work, face recognition is implemented with a novel approach. The SVD based HMMs are modeled by modifying the singular values of the state matrices. The features are extracted as singular values and then instead of directly feeding the singular values as the features, it is combined linearly to derive another set of features. The optimum value for the linear combination factor is derived by conducting several simulations on two training datasets of ORL database. The original SVD based HMM is a special case of the linearly combined SVD based HMM that is developed as part of this research work. The improvement is the accuracy with the proposed approach is compared with the standard SVD based HMM and also over the PCA and LBP for the ORL database.

Index Terms—Hidden Markov Models, HMM, Face Recognition, Sequential models.

I. Introduction

Face recognition is a very important application of image processing methods in which the facial image is used to identify with the person. The person is identified with the facial images stored in the database. The image that is being tested is presented to the face recognition system and the matching facial image is identified from the database. Based on identification of the image, the next actions are decided. For example if there is a necessity to identify a criminal in an airport, the face recognition system compares the facial images of all the people in the airport present at the point of time, one after the other, with the facial images of the database and checks if the matching face has any criminal background. In such a case, the accuracy of the face recognition system must be as high as possible. In order to achieve this, there are many face recognition methods developed, but the Hidden Markov Models (HMM) are very good models in terms achieving high recognition rates. The HMM was originally developed in 1970s. However, the HMMs were practically applies to solve the real life problems in 1994 by Samaria & Young [1]. The face recognition with HMM involves five states. The five states include the forehead, eye, nose, mouth and the chin. The HMM is very good in modeling the five states in a sequential pattern. The other methods like PCA or LBP do not model the face recognition method sequentially. That is the major difference between the HMM and other feature based recognition systems. Also the HMM do not get affected much with the orientation, illumination, expression or size of the face in the image. Various factors of HMM that affect the performance is investigated in ref [2]. In that research work experiments were conducted to measure the performance of HMMs and it was finally observed that HMMs yield better results than that of the Eigen face methods. Nefian.et.al [3] developed a new methodology to estimate the states by using observation vectors in HMM. The HMM was developed with coefficients of the Karhunen Loeve transform and it reduced the computational complexity of the algorithm significantly. Phad.et al. [4] developed a method known as Embedded HMM or EHMM that uses both feature and score levels. There are many parameters in the EHMM that can be varied to get the required recognition rate. Chihaaoui.et.al. [5] developed a HMM along with the LBP model. LBP was used to extract the features and those features are input to the HMM for face recognition. The HMM-LBP has been designed with four stages. In first stage, the facial image is divided into multiple blocks, the features are extracted from each block with LBP, the probabilities are estimated for each feature and then maximum probability is chosen. With this approach, authors proved that the face recognition rate with HMM-LBP is much better than that of all the existing methods at that time.

Sanderson et al. used Multi-Region Probabilistic Histograms for Robust and Scalable Identity Inference for the face recognition purpose [6]. This method also improved the recognition rates significantly. Sandeep Saxena et al. [7] has combined the HMM with the ANN and developed a unified HMM-ANN model to demonstrate that the recognition rates can be improved if the ANNs are used along with the Hidden Markov Models.

Other notable improvements in the face recognition were contributed by Kanade et al. [8] with the help of picture processing by computer and recognition of human Faces. Turk et al. used the Eigen faces in the face recognition

systems [9]. Wiskott et al. used elastic bunch graph matching in the face recognition method [10]. Very important development in the area of face recognition was the usage of neural network models (ANN) by Lin et al in 1997 [11]. Markov random fields were used by Huang et al. [12] and HMMs were used along with the wavelets by Bicego et al. [13]. Kohir et al. used DCT coefficients as the features in the HMM models [14] and Pooya. et al. developed a new face recognition system using the singular values if SVD as feature vectors [15].

II. Probability Model

The face of a human being has the features like forehead, eyes, nose, mouth and chin in the order from top to bottom of the face. These features are in the same order for all the human beings. Hence the hidden markov models (HMM) are suitable to address the face recognition problem by taking advantage of the same order of the features in the subjects or objects being recognized. In a HMM, there are two matrices namely, transition matrix and the emitting probability matrix. There are N states in a data point. Since every state in the series should always have preceding and a proceeding state in a markov model, total number of states in the model becomes N+2.

Let

Λ : Hidden Markov Model

A : The state transition probability matrix, where $A = \{a_{ij}\}$ and the state sequence is provided by S_t .

B : Observation probability matrix, where $B = \{b_j(k)\}$

Π : Initial state distribution

The HMM can be defined as

$$\Lambda = (A, B, \Pi) \quad (1)$$

Let the observation sequence is given by

$$X = [x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_T] \quad (2)$$

The probability density function of a the emitting state is

$$p(X | S_t, \Lambda).$$

Therefore the HMM can be defined as

$$\Lambda = \{A, p\} \quad (3)$$

The match between model Λ and the observation sequence X_1^T can be derived as $p(X_1^T | \Lambda)$. The image has vertical and horizontal pixel values. The pixels can be grouped into blocks. For example, 8x8 pixels can be considered as a block and the whole image can now be represented as a set of blocks and each block has 8x8 pixels. The block can approximated with any other features like DCT coefficients, Eigen values or singular values. The image now represented by blocks and the blocks are represented by not the pixel values but by other transformed parameter like DCT coefficients, Eigen values or singular values. The image can be divided as vertical states or the horizontal states. Each vertical state is as a HMM distribution $p(X_1^T | \Lambda)$. Similarly, the horizontal HMM can also be treated as another distribution. For every state in the vertical direction, the

$$p(X | S_t, \Lambda) \rightarrow \Lambda_i(A_i, p_i). \quad (4)$$

Figure 1: HMM distributions for each state

Each state in the image can be approximated with a Gaussian mixture model as shown in Fig. 1, as

$$\Psi(x) = \sum_{j=1}^J p(j) N_k(x) \quad (5)$$

where, $\Psi(x)$ is a weighted sum of J Gaussian distributions and $N_k(x)$ is the d-dimensional Gaussian distribution with mean μ and co-variance matrix Σ .

$$N_k(x | \mu, \Sigma) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{d}{2}} |\Sigma|^{\frac{1}{2}}} e^{\left[-\frac{1}{2} (x - \mu)^T \Sigma^{-1} (x - \mu) \right]} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\sum_{j=1}^J p(j) = 1 \quad (7)$$

The state matrix Ψ can be factorized into U, S and V matrices using the singular value decomposition. That is

$$\Psi(x) = U S V^T \quad (8)$$

Where S is the matrix of singular values $\Psi_1, \Psi_2, \Psi_3, \dots, \Psi_N$ and it can be used as features in the HMM. Usually, the features for the HMM can be selected from vectors of U matrix and some of the singular values from S matrix. That is U (1,1), $\Psi_1, \Psi_2, \Psi_3, \dots, \Psi_n$. But in this work, instead of considering the singular values $\Psi_1, \Psi_2, \Psi_3, \dots, \Psi_n$, the linear combination of the singular values are considered as the features. That is, the new features in a generalized form are,

$$S_i = \beta_i \Psi_i + \beta_{i+1} \Psi_{i+1} + \beta_{i+2} \Psi_{i+2} + \dots + \beta_n \Psi_n \quad (9)$$

$$S_{i+1} = \beta_{i+1} \Psi_{i+1} + \beta_{i+2} \Psi_{i+2} + \beta_{i+3} \Psi_{i+3} + \dots + \beta_{i+n} \Psi_{i+n} \quad (10)$$

Where

$$\beta_1 + \beta_2 + \beta_3 + \dots + \beta_n = 1 \quad (10)$$

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Or

$$\sum_{n=1}^{N_s} \beta_n = 1 \quad (11)$$

The values for β_n can be derived with any optimization algorithm or by means of trial and error.

If the number of singular values to be considered only two to estimate S_i , then, the

$$S_1 = \alpha \Psi_1 + (1 - \alpha) \Psi_2 \quad (12)$$

$$S_2 = \alpha \Psi_2 + (1 - \alpha) \Psi_3 \quad (13)$$

Where,

$$\beta_1 = \alpha \text{ and } \beta_2 = 1 - \alpha \quad (14)$$

The HMM can be optimized using the Baum Welch algorithm or Viterbi algorithm.

III. Simulation Results

In this paper, the simulations are performed on the ORL database. The database has images of 40 persons, of which 36 images belong to males and the remaining 4 belong to females. Each person has 10 images of different facial expressions. Hence there are a total of 400 images in the database. The 400 images are split into two parts of equal size, i.e. 200 images in each group. One group of images is used for the training purpose and the other group is used for test purpose. Fig. 2 shows the training images of 5 people (facial expression 1,3,5,7 and 9). Each person has the 5 different facial expressions. Similarly, the test images of each person with five different facial expression (facial expression 2,4,6,8 and 10) is shown in Fig. 3. Actually, there are five different facial expressions for each of 40 persons in both and training and test sets, the Figs. 2 and 3 are only shown for representative purpose. The images have different light conditions, but the background is set as uniform as possible.

Figure 2: Images for training

Figure 3: Images for testing

The features are provided to the HMM models in the form of the singular values or linear combination of singular values derived from the singular value decomposition. The image is reduced in size from the original size of 94x112 to 46x56. There are 46 columns in the images. For each state, the numbers of rows considered are 5 and the numbers of columns considered are 46. Now, each state is represented by a matrix of size 5 x 46. In each image there are 52 states. The features of each state are extracted using the singular values with the help of SVD. Each state matrix is subjected singular value decomposition. The SVD produces matrices U, S and V. The U matrix is of size 5 x 5, S matrix is of size 5 x 46 and V matrix is of size 46 x 46. The state of the matrix is represented by the first element in the U matrix and the first two singular values. That is $U(1,1)$ and Ψ_1 and Ψ_2 .

In the dataset, since each of the persons has 10 different facial expressions (FE), five facial expressions are used for training purpose and the remaining five facial expressions are used for test purpose. Table 1 shows the results for the face recognition by the SVD based HMM algorithm (SVD-HMM) for five different facial expressions and the images recognized. In case of 1st person, when FE1 was presented, the HMM recognized 26th person instead of person 1, and hence it is a failure. For person 2, the person was rightly recognized when the entire facial expressions are tested. Overall, there is an accuracy of 94%.

Table 1: Recognized images by SVD-HMM for the training set was formed by the facial expression 1,3,5,7 and 9 and the test set was formed by the images 2,4,6,8 and 10

Person in Test	FE1	FE2	FE3	FE4	FE5
1	26	1	1	6	1
2	2	2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4	4	4
5	18	5	5	5	5
6	6	6	6	6	6
7	7	7	7	7	7
8	8	8	8	8	8
9	9	9	9	9	9
10	4	10	10	10	10
11	11	11	11	11	11

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12	12	12	12	12	12
13	13	13	13	13	13
14	14	14	14	14	14
15	15	15	15	36	15
16	16	16	16	16	16
17	17	17	17	17	17
18	18	18	18	18	18
19	19	19	19	19	23
20	20	20	20	20	20
21	21	39	21	21	21
22	22	22	22	22	22
23	23	23	23	23	23
24	24	24	15	24	24
25	25	25	25	25	25
26	26	26	26	26	26
27	27	27	27	27	27
28	28	28	28	28	28
29	29	29	29	29	29
30	30	30	30	30	30
31	31	31	31	31	31
32	32	32	32	32	32
33	33	33	33	33	33
34	34	34	34	34	34
35	35	35	25	35	35
36	36	36	36	36	36
37	37	37	37	37	37
38	38	38	38	38	38
39	39	39	39	39	39
40	40	40	13	18	18

In this research work, a new approach (LIN-SVD-HMM) has been proposed to increase the accuracy of the method. Instead of using the top two singular values, the linear combination of the singular values can be used with a linear combination factor as shown in Eqs. 12 and 13. It can be observed from Eqs. 8 and 9 that three singular values can be used to derive two pseudo singular values S_1 and S_2 . Now the each state is defined with $U(1,1)$, S_1 and S_2 instead of $U(1,1)$, Ψ_1 and Ψ_2 . With this approach, the question that remains is the value for α . The optimum value for alpha is determined varying the value from 1.0 to 0.6 with a decrement of 0.1. When the α is set to 1.0, it is equivalent to using the $U(1,1)$, Ψ_1 and Ψ_2 to define the states.

Table 2: Recognized images by LIN-SVD-HMM when $\alpha = 0.7$ for the training set was formed by the facial expression 1,3,5,7 and 9 and the test set was formed by the images 2,4,6,8 and 10

Person in Test	FE1	FE2	FE3	FE4	FE5
1	25	1	1	1	1
2	2	2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4	4	4
5	1	5	5	5	5
6	6	6	6	6	6
7	7	7	7	7	7
8	8	8	8	8	8
9	38	9	9	9	9
10	19	10	10	10	10
11	11	11	11	11	11
12	12	12	12	12	12
13	13	13	13	13	13

14	14	14	14	14	14
15	15	15	15	15	15
16	16	16	16	16	16
17	17	17	17	17	17
18	18	18	18	18	18
19	19	19	19	19	19
20	20	20	20	20	20
21	21	21	21	21	21
22	22	22	22	22	22
23	23	23	23	23	23
24	24	24	15	24	24
25	25	25	25	25	25
26	26	26	26	26	26
27	27	27	27	27	27
28	28	28	28	28	28
29	29	29	29	29	29
30	30	30	30	30	30
31	31	31	31	31	31
32	32	32	32	32	32
33	33	33	30	33	33
34	34	34	34	34	34
35	35	35	25	35	35
36	36	36	36	36	36
37	37	37	37	37	37
38	38	38	38	38	38
39	39	39	39	39	39
40	40	40	18	18	18

When α is set to 0.7, the overall face recognition accuracy is improved to 95%. When α was 1.0, the over accuracy was at 94%. That means there is 1% improvement in the accuracy this improvement in accuracy can be attributed to the third singular value that is considered in the proposed approach (LIN-SVD-HMM). %. When α was 1.0 the third singular value Ψ_3 vanished from Eqs. 9 and 10.

Figure 4: Accuracy of HMM for different α values for the training set was formed by the facial expression 1,3,5,7 and 9 and the test set was formed by the images 2,4,6,8 and 10.

Simulations were performed to determine the optimum value for α which will yield the highest accuracy for face recognition by the HMM. The α was varied from 0.6 to 1.0 and at the value of $\alpha = 0.9$, the accuracy was highest with 96%. The original method where the top two singular values are directly used as parameters of the states, the accuracy was just 94%. This case is equivalent to setting the α as 1.0.

Figure 5: Accuracy of LBP, PCA and HMM based methods

Fig. 5 shows the accuracy of LBP, PCA and HMM based face recognition methods when the same datasets were tested. PCA has yielded an accuracy was at 92.5% and LBP produced 79.5% accuracy. The original SVD based HMM is at 94% and the proposed method (LIN-SVD-HMM) in the research wok has yield 96%. Therefore the proposed methodology (LIN-SVD-HMM) has improved the accuracy of the face recognition by 2% over the original SVD-HMM method and 3.5% over the PCA.

As a second case, the training set was formed by the facial expression 1,3,6,8 and 9 and the test set was formed by the images 2,4,5,7 and 10.

Table 3: Recognized images by SVD-HMM when $\alpha = 1.0$

Person in Test	FE1	FE2	FE3	FE4	FE5
1	26	1	1	1	1
2	2	2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4	4	4
5	1	5	5	5	5
6	6	6	6	6	6
7	7	7	36	7	7
8	8	8	8	8	8
9	9	9	9	9	9
10	4	10	10	10	10
11	11	11	11	11	11
12	12	12	12	12	12
13	13	25	25	13	13
14	14	14	14	14	14
15	15	15	15	15	15
16	16	16	16	19	19
17	17	17	17	17	17
18	18	18	18	18	18
19	19	19	19	19	19
20	20	20	20	33	20
21	21	39	21	21	21
22	22	22	22	22	22
23	23	23	23	23	23
24	24	24	24	24	24
25	25	25	25	25	25
26	26	26	26	26	26
27	27	27	27	27	27
28	28	28	28	28	28
29	29	29	29	29	29

30	30	33	30	30	30
31	31	31	31	31	31
32	32	32	32	32	32
33	33	33	33	33	33
34	34	34	34	34	34
35	35	15	35	35	35
36	36	36	36	36	36
37	37	37	37	37	37
38	38	38	38	38	38
39	39	39	39	39	39
40	40	40	40	40	18

Table 3 shows the results for the face recognition by the LIN-SVD-HMM for $\alpha = 1.0$ (equivalent to SVD-HMM) for five different facial expressions and the images recognized. There is an accuracy of 93.5%.

When α is set to 0.9 and at 0,7, the accuracy is improved to 94.5%. The results are presented in Table 4 and Fig. 6.

Table 4: Recognized images by LIN-SVD-HMM when $\alpha = 0.9$

Person in Test	FE1	FE2	FE3	FE4	FE5
1	26	1	1	1	1
2	2	2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4	4	4
5	18	5	5	5	5
6	6	6	6	6	6
7	7	7	36	7	7
8	8	8	8	8	8
9	9	9	9	9	9
10	19	10	10	10	10
11	11	11	11	11	11
12	12	12	12	12	12
13	13	25	25	14	13
14	14	14	14	14	14
15	15	15	15	15	15
16	16	16	16	16	16
17	17	17	17	17	17
18	18	18	18	18	18
19	19	19	19	19	19
20	20	20	33	33	20
21	21	21	21	21	21
22	22	22	22	22	22
23	23	23	23	23	23
24	24	24	24	24	24
25	25	25	25	25	25
26	26	26	26	26	26
27	27	27	27	27	27
28	28	28	28	28	28
29	29	29	29	29	29
30	30	33	30	30	30
31	31	31	31	31	31
32	32	32	32	32	32
33	33	33	33	33	33
34	34	34	34	34	34

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35	35	9	35	35	35
36	36	36	36	36	36
37	37	37	37	37	37
38	38	38	38	38	38
39	39	39	39	39	39
40	40	40	40	40	40

Figure 6: Accuracy of HMM for different α values for the training set was formed by the facial expression 1,3,6,8 and 9 and the test set was formed by the images 2,4,5,7 and 10

Figure 7: Accuracy of LBP, PCA and HMM based methods

Fig. 7 shows the accuracy of LBP, PCA and HMM based face recognition methods for the training set was formed by the facial expression 1,3,6,8 and 9 and the test set was formed by the images 2,4,5,7 and 10. With this dataset, the accuracy was at 91.5% with PCA and 80.5% with LBP. The original SVD based HMM is at 93.5% and the LIN-SVD-HMM has yield 94.5% when the α is set to 0.9 or 0.7. The value if alpha needed to found for each dataset used for training. For the ORL database, the alpha is found be optimum at 0.9 for the maximum recognition rate.

IV. Conclusion

In this work, a new method is proposed based on the hidden markov models. The HMM models are developed based on the singular value decomposition. The features are extracted using the singular values. In the proposed method, the largest singular values are linearly combined to define the features. In original SVD-HMM, the singular values are directly used, but in the proposed LIN-SVD-HMM, the singular values are linearly combined instead. In LIN-SVD-HMM, three singular values are used while only two singular values are used in SVD-HMM. The accuracy of the recognition is tested for two different datasets formed with ORL database. In both the cases, the accuracy of LIN-SVD-HMM has yielded better accuracy than SVD-HMM. In case of the first data set (Training: 1,3,5,7 and 9), the accuracy of LIN-SVD-HMM was 96% whereas, the accuracy of SVD-HMM was 94%. Similarly, for second data set (Training: 1,3,6,8 and 9), the accuracy of LIN-SVD-HMM was 94.5% whereas; the accuracy of SVD-HMM was 93.5%. The SVD-HMM based methods are also compared with the PCA and LBP for these

datasets. Hence, the proposed method using the linear combination of singular values (LIN-SVD-HMM) has much better accuracy than the SVD-HMM, PCA and LBP.

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